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Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	7
2.	Variables considered	8
3.	Pilot cases	11
3.1.	Corby's dwelling pilot experience	11
3.1.1.	CHESS SETUP system implemented	11
3.1.2.	Data collection periods.....	12
3.1.3.	CHESS SETUP system operation and performance	13
3.1.3.1.	Building Energy consumption.....	13
3.1.3.2.	Energy savings	16
3.1.3.3.	Seasonal thermal energy storage.....	20
3.1.3.4.	Heat Pump performance.....	22
3.1.4.	Corby's dwelling CHESS SETUP system implementation impact.....	23
3.2.	Lavola Ecobuilding pilot experience.....	26
3.2.1	CHESS SETUP system implemented	26
3.2.2.	Data collection periods.....	28
3.2.3.	CHESS SETUP system operation and performance	29
3.2.3.1.	Building energy consumption.....	29
3.2.3.2.	Energy savings	31
3.2.3.3.	Heat Pump performance	36
3.2.3.4.	Seasonal thermal energy storage.....	38
3.2.4.	Lavola's CHESS SETUP system implementation impact	39
3.3.	Sports Centre (Eurofitness) Sant Cugat pilot experience.....	41
3.3.1.	CHESS SETUP system implemented	41
3.3.2.	Data collection periods.....	42
3.3.3.	CHESS SETUP system operation and performance	43
3.3.3.1.	Building energy consumption.....	43
3.3.3.2.	Energy savings	45
3.3.3.3.	Seasonal thermal energy storage.....	51
3.3.3.4.	Heat Pump performance.....	54
3.3.4.	Sant Cugat's CHESS SETUP system implementation impact	55
4.	Conclusions.....	57
5.	Annex.....	58

Figures

Figure 1: Main variables studied to evaluate the CHESSE SETUP implementation.....	8
Figure 2: Total demands group variables.....	8
Figure 3: System configuration main variables	8
Figure 4: System operation main variables.....	9
Figure 5: Energy savings variables group.....	9
Figure 6: Economic variables considered.....	9
Figure 7: Corby's dwelling schematic CHESSE SETUP system.....	11
Figure 8: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored	16
Figure 9: Corby's average Eco-home CHESSE SETUP system consumption and production.....	17
Figure 10: Monthly Eco-homes average electrical performance	17
Figure 11: Corby's Eco-home plot 45 average hourly electrical consumption and production for different months.....	19
Figure 12: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions per Eco-home.....	20
Figure 13: STES monthly average temperatures.....	21
Figure 14: Plot 44 EEB temperatures variation for the period June 24 th to 26 th , 2020	22
Figure 15: Outside Average temperature vs CHESSE SETUP system average monthly EER.....	23
Figure 16: Lavola's Ecobuilding schematic CHESSE SETUP system.....	27
Figure 17: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored	31
Figure 18: PV production, Ecobuilding energy demand, and CHESSE SETUP system energy consumption.....	33
Figure 19: CHESSE SETUP average daily electrical consumption and production for different months	34
Figure 20: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions	35
Figure 21: Lavola's Ecobuilding outdoor average monthly temperatures	37
Figure 22: Outside Average temperature vs CHESSE SETUP system average monthly EER and COP	37
Figure 23: Sant Cugat's Sports Centre schematic CHESSE SETUP system	41
Figure 24: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored period	44
Figure 25: CHESSE SETUP system energy demand.....	47
Figure 26: CHESSE SETUP electrical consumption and production.....	48
Figure 27: CHESSE SETUP average daily electrical consumption and production for different months	49
Figure 28: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions to supply the Sports Centre thermal demand.....	49

Figure 29: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions to supply the 'swimming-pool water' heating demand. 50

Figure 30: STES daily average temperatures vs. outdoor average temperature 51

Figure 31: Swimming pool and STES thermal variations, and temperatures between January 28th and February 10th. 52

Figure 32: STES monthly average temperatures 52

Figure 33: STES monthly average temperatures vs. outdoor monthly average temperatures..... 53

Figure 34: Swimming pool and STES thermal variations, and temperatures between January 26th and 27th. 53

Figure 35: CHESSETUP system average monthly COP 55

Tables

Table 1: Corby's dwellings CHESSE SETUP system components.....	12
Table 2: Average energy demand values for each of the houses. Source: Deliverable 3.7	14
Table 3: Comparative table between CHESSE SETUP thermal energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Corby's Eco-homes.....	15
Table 4: CHESSE SETUP heat pump energy performance.....	22
Table 5: Results of the CHESSE SETUP system implementation for Corby's dwellings pilot experience	25
Table 6: Different CHESSE SETUP system configurations proposed for Lavola's Ecobuilding.....	27
Table 7: Lavola's Ecobuilding CHESSE SETUP system components	28
Table 8: Energy demand of Lavola's Ecobuilding. Source: Deliverable 3.7.....	29
Table 9: Monitored energy demand Lavola's Ecobuilding 2019-2020.....	30
Table 10: Comparative table between CHESSE SETUP thermal energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Lavola's pilot	32
Table 11: CHESSE SETUP heat pump energy performance	36
Table 12: Simulated vs monitored CHESSE SETUP system implementation impacts for Lavola's Ecobuilding	40
Table 13: Sant Cugat's CHESSE SETUP system components.....	42
Table 14: Energy demand of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre. Source: Deliverable 3.7	43
Table 15: Monitored thermal demand Sant Cugat's Sports Centre 2019-2020	44
Table 16: Comparative table between CHESSE SETUP energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre	46
Table 17: CHESSE SETUP heat pump energy performance	54
Table 18: Simulated vs monitored CHESSE SETUP system implementation impacts for Sant Cugat's Sports Centre.....	56

1. Introduction

The main objective of this document is to elaborate a synthesized report, for each CHES-SETUP pilot experience, where data obtained from the monitoring and control system are compared with theoretical data obtained from the simulations.

For Lavola Ecoedifici and Sant Cugat Sports Centre, the empirical values were obtained from the monitoring and control system implemented in these two pilots, described in the deliverable '4.2 Management tool'. For Corby's dwellings, the implemented solution has its own control system and the empirical values were obtained from this one.

The theoretical values for each pilot are those obtained in the simulations performed in the deliverable 'D3.7 Pilot's experience report' and those calculated in the deliverable 'D5.1 Construction Plan Report'.

As part of the results report, a general scheme of the system installed in each pilot is presented, indicating its main components and the operation mode for each case.

2. Variables considered

The variables studied to evaluate the operation and performances of the pilots were grouped in five different blocks as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Main variables studied to evaluate the CHESSE SETUP implementation

The first studied block (i.e. total demand) defines the building energy demands for a specific time period. In addition, it is also specified on which of these energy demands the CHESSE-SETUP system acts. Figure 2 shows the main variables considered in this block: Heating and Domestic Hot Water, Cooling and Electricity.

Figure 2: Total demands group variables

The second block (i.e. system configuration) includes the variables related to the configuration parameters of the pilots. In this block, there is no comparison between simulated and monitored values, since these are different fixed parameters for each one of the pilots. Figure 3 shows the variables considered in this group for the analysis.

Figure 3: System configuration main variables

As shown in Figure 4, the Operation block includes the variables related to the CHESSE-SETUP system operation for each pilot. The variables included are heat pump energy consumption (HP cons.), energy efficiency ratio¹ (EER), electrical and thermal energy

¹ This is a measure of the ratio of delivered thermal power to total electrical power. This includes ancillaries such as any fans, pumps and controls.

production, seasonal thermal energy storage (STES) temperatures, and the back-up system energy consumption.

Figure 4: System operation main variables.

The Energy Savings block groups the variables related to the total energy savings obtained by the CHESSETUP system (in kWh/yr. and in %), for each pilot (Figure 5). In this group of variables are also included the 'CHESSEnergy savings' that represent the percentage of energy saved comparing the original heating and DHW system performance with the new CHESSETUP system installed. Finally, the GHG emission savings are also included in this group (in kg CO₂/year and in %).

Figure 5: Energy savings variables group.

Finally, the Economics group lists those variables related to the installation, maintenance, and operation costs, economic savings generated, and paybacks for each pilot (Figure 6). The economic analysis of the results of each of the pilots is developed in the deliverable 'D6.1 Business model analysis for the case studies' and is based on the results obtained in this deliverable.

Figure 6: Economic variables considered

The following section develops a detailed analysis of the implemented CHESSE SETUP system performance for each pilot. The results obtained from the monitoring are compared with the results obtained in deliverables D3.7 and D5.1, and with the 'baseline' case that assumes the thermal demand is 100% covered by a natural gas boiler.

It should be noted that in none of the three pilots studied the user's comfort conditions have been affected. This is one of the main objectives of the monitoring and control system. In case that the CHESSE SETUP system cannot supply the thermal demand, the back-up system automatically goes on to satisfy it, not affecting the user's comfort.

3. Pilot cases

3.1. Corby's dwelling pilot experience

3.1.1. CHESS SETUP system implemented

The CHESS SETUP system implemented in Corby's consists of 26 prototypes for eco-home buildings. The homes were built on the popular development of Priors Hall Park in Corby, Northamptonshire. This means that the houses will be very representative of the average new houses in the UK, and perhaps, it could also be said that in the rest of Europe.

Figure 7 shows the schematic CHESS SETUP system implemented in Corby's dwellings. The main elements are represented: solar hybrid and photovoltaic panels, earth energy bank (EEB), ground source heat pump, buffer tank, and dwelling thermal demand (heating and Domestic Hot Water).

Figure 7: Corby's dwelling schematic CHESS SETUP system

Table 1 summarizes the main components used for the implementation of CHESS SETUP system; these components have been described in 'D5.1 Construction Plan Report'.

System components	Characteristics
Hybrid panels	Solar Angel DG-01 (59 % thermal efficiency, 16 % electric efficiency) 2,25 kWp 14,4 m ² 9 panels Slope (Roof integrated)
Photovoltaic panels	Romag 60 (16,2 % electric efficiency) 2,75 kWp 17,7 m ² 11 panels Slope (Roof integrated)
Seasonal Thermal Storage Tank	Earth energy bank 21-24 underground boreholes (1,5 meters deep)
Battery	Lithium BYD B-PLUS 2.5 2,5 kWh flexible module
Water-water heat pump	AquaMaster AQ221C Heat Power 3 kW COP 4,3
Buffer tank	170 litres 55°C set-point temperature

Table 1: Corby's dwellings CHESS SETUP system components.

3.1.2. Data collection periods

The beginning of the studied period for Corby's dwellings case study depends on three different events: the monitoring and control system start-up, the system commissioning and finally the entry of the new housing occupants.

In June 2019 the monitoring system it started to receive data for the first four plots (44, 45, 46 and 47). This initial data gathered data had no value for their direct analysis since the dwellings were not inhabited, but it served to observe some inconsistencies on the collection. The greatest challenge remains connectivity and stability of data supply. The time lag between problems being identified (usually a lack of connection or inconsistent data) and being able to identify and address the cause has caused a lot of work and was compound by the lockdown due to COVID-19 pandemic.

It was not until January 2020 that the first dwellings were inhabited. That created the possibility to receive data from inhabited dwellings. An additional impact of the lockdown has been on home occupation, in that, new moves have not been possible and those in the homes are using them very differently from normal use.

Therefore, there is access to monitoring data for four homes since June 2019, but inconsistently. The first data available from inhabited homes is from January 2020. In

March 2020 the emergency lockdown was activated in the UK due to COVID-19. It was not until June 2020, that there was access to all the information necessary to analyse the performance of the systems implemented. The data analysis is carried out showing the mean of the values collected in the 4 monitored homes.

The data collected from June 2020 until now, will be used to compare with the simulations developed in deliverables D3.7 and D5.1. In this way 'verify' the correct functioning of the system during the monitored period. The real potential of the system (consumption, production, savings, etc.) cannot be defined due to the short period with consistent data, which also corresponds to the summer season, as the CHESSE SETUP system "charges" the EEB during this period presents its greatest potential benefit in the cold months.

Due to the above, the analysis of the system data is carried out in two stages. First, the CHESSE SETUP system performance is analysed in the period June 2020 to September 2020, with real values obtained from the pilots monitoring. Secondly, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

3.1.3. CHESSE SETUP system operation and performance

3.1.3.1. Building Energy consumption

As mentioned in the deliverable 'D3.7 Pilot's experience report', the houses only use electricity, and not use natural gas. The energy for heating comes from the Earth Energy Bank, where the stored heat is transferred to the homes and apartments for use when needed using a water-source heat pump. Each house has its own Earth Energy Bank for seasonal thermal storage.

Energy analysis conducted has defined that the estimated total energy consumption from houses will be around 5.400 kWh_e/year. Therefore the total annual energy consumption of all 26 houses will be around 140 MWh_e/year. Table 2 shows the broken-down values for the average home energy.

Around 4.200 kWh_t/year of thermal energy will be transferred to the heat pump. 3.000 kWh_t/year of thermal energy will then be used for Domestic Hot Water (DHW), and another 3.000 kWh_t/year of thermal energy will be used for under-floor heating. Therefore, in order to keep up with demand, another 2.000 kWh_e/year of electricity will be used by the heat pump on top of the 4.200 kWh_t/year of generated thermal energy.

Month	PV (kWh _e)	PV-Thermal (kWh _t)	Power demand ² (kWh _e)	CHESSE SETUP ³ cons. (kWh _e)	Other elect. cons. ⁴ (kWh _e)	Thermal Output (kWh _t)	EER	Energy Costs (€)	Emissions (kgCO ₂)
Jan.	126,3	440,5	578,3	294,0	284,3	766,8	2,6	94,77 €	115,6
Feb.	199,4	456,7	571,8	287,5	284,3	740,3	2,6	78,05 €	95,2
Mar.	350,6	515,9	494,6	210,3	284,3	606,7	2,9	30,19 €	36,8
Apr.	464,0	483,7	470,6	186,3	284,3	581,4	3,1	1,38 €	1,7
May.	561,5	463,7	419,1	134,8	284,3	463,8	3,4	-29,85 €	-36,4
Jun.	575,4	379,3	377,4	93,0	284,3	348,7	3,7	-41,51 €	-50,6
Jul.	580,4	306,1	349,9	65,6	284,3	260,2	4,0	-48,33 €	-58,9
Aug.	510,2	273,5	360,2	75,9	284,3	302,9	4,0	-31,45 €	-38,3
Sep.	383,2	221,7	378,4	94,1	284,3	356,1	3,8	-0,99 €	-1,2
Oct.	260,6	216,4	427,4	143,1	284,3	493,0	3,4	34,98 €	42,6
Nov.	143,5	182,3	484,3	199,9	284,3	601,4	3,0	71,43 €	87,1
Dec.	114,2	289,1	545,3	261,0	284,3	707,5	2,7	90,38 €	110,2
TOTAL	4.269,3	4.228,8	5.457,4	2.045,4	3.412,0	6.228,8	3,04	249,06 €	303,7

Table 2: Average energy demand values for each of the houses. Source: Deliverable 3.7

These figures were used in 'D3.7 Pilot experience report' and 'D5.1 Construction plan report' to carry out the simulation and dimensioning of the CHESSE SETUP system, as they are considered representative thermal demands.

Table 3 shows the average thermal demands corresponding to the period June-September 2020, for the 4 monitored homes. The rest of the year's system performance (grey rows) has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation, D3.7 results and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

² Total electrical building demand

³ Heat pump consumption including auxiliaries' equipment.

⁴ Electrical loads such as lighting, consumer electronics, and cold appliances, among others.

Corby's Eco-home															
CHESS SETUP system implemented ⁵								Baseline							
Month	PV (kWh _e)	Power demand ⁶ (kWh _e)	CHESS SETUP cons. ⁷ (kWh _e)	Other elect. cons. ⁸ (kWh _e)	Thermal Output (kWh _t)	EER	Energy Cost (€)	Emissions (kgCO ₂)	Boiler (kWh _{pci})	Energy cost (€)	Power demand (kWh _e)	Energy Costs (€)	Total Energy (kWh)	Total Costs (€)	Emissions (kgCO ₂)
Jan.	126,3	649,5	365,2	284,3	766,8	2,1	109,69 €	143,8	852,0	45,48 €	284,3	59,61 €	1136,4	105,09 €	229,45
Feb.	199,4	620,9	336,5	284,3	740,3	2,2	88,34 €	123,7	822,6	43,91 €	284,3	59,61 €	1106,9	103,51 €	224,03
Mar.	350,6	527,0	242,7	284,3	606,7	2,5	36,98 €	73,1	674,1	35,98 €	284,3	59,61 €	958,4	95,59 €	196,71
Apr.	640,3	302,3	186,3	116,0	581,4	3,1	-70,86 €	-35,2	646,0	34,48 €	116,0	24,32 €	762,0	58,80 €	148,51
May.	418,9	223,7	134,8	88,9	463,8	3,4	-40,93 €	-16,4	515,3	27,51 €	88,9	18,64 €	604,3	46,15 €	117,55
Jun.	682,7	388,9	108,4	280,5	325,0	3,0	-61,59 €	-20,5	361,1	19,27 €	280,5	58,81 €	641,6	78,09 €	138,15
Jul.	592,0	369,3	108,7	260,6	312,3	2,9	-46,68 €	-9,6	347,0	18,52 €	260,6	54,63 €	607,6	73,15 €	130,45
Aug.	641,6	387,4	110,8	276,6	346,2	3,1	-53,29 €	5,7	384,7	20,53 €	276,6	57,97 €	661,2	78,51 €	141,47
Sep.	383,2	407,1	122,8	284,3	356,1	2,9	5,03 €	15,9	395,7	21,12 €	284,3	59,61 €	680,0	80,73 €	145,48
Oct.	260,6	460,4	176,1	284,3	493,0	2,8	41,89 €	71,9	547,8	29,24 €	284,3	59,61 €	832,1	88,84 €	173,46
Nov.	143,5	524,9	240,6	284,3	601,4	2,5	79,95 €	109,0	668,3	35,67 €	284,3	59,61 €	952,6	95,28 €	195,64
Dec.	114,2	591,9	307,6	284,3	707,5	2,3	100,15 €	131,2	786,1	41,96 €	284,3	59,61 €	1070,4	101,57 €	217,32
TOTAL	4.553,3	5.453,4	2.440,4	3.013,0	6.300,5	2,6	188,69 €	592,8	7.000,6	373,68 €	3.013,0	631,62 €	10.013,0	1.005,30 €	2.058,23

Table 3: Comparative table between CHESS SETUP thermal energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Corby's Eco-homes

⁵ Mean values obtained from the monitoring of plots 44, 45, 46 and 47.

⁶ Total electrical building demand.

⁷ Heat pump consumption including auxiliaries' equipment.

⁸ Electrical loads such as lighting, consumer electronics, and cold appliances, among others.

Comparing Table 2 and Table 3, a total demand increase of 3,7 % is observed on average Corby's house for the monitored period. As mentioned above, this may be due to user-defined comfort settings, or even spending more time in the house due to confinement.

Figure 8 shows that the increase in thermal demand, comparing both monitored periods (from Jun to September), may be due to the longer time of occupation and use of the house due to confinement. In the same figure, it is also observed that the average 'Power demand' presents a decrease in the period from March to May. This may be due to the fact that not all monitored houses were occupied during this period.

Figure 8: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored

Therefore, the analysis is focused on comparing data obtained from the monitoring, with the results obtained from the simulation.

3.1.3.2. Energy savings

The system studied combines thermal generation coming from the hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage performed in the thermal energy storage in the form of an earth energy bank, and the use of a high-efficiency ground source heat pump.

The average Corby's Eco-home energy savings has been estimated in Table 3. The 'Baseline' case was also studied, where all home thermal demand, heating and domestic hot water, is supposed to be covered by a natural gas boiler system.

The CHESSE SETUP system provide 7.000 kWh_{pci} estimated primary thermal energy savings per house, as it is the amount of natural gas that has been estimated to be saved as thermal energy of Eco-home heating demand. On the other hand, an average annual electrical energy consumption of 6.300 kWh_e is estimated, and an electrical energy production of 4.550 kWh_e, which would represent a 72 % saving of electrical energy consumption from the grid.

In the monitored period, the energy supplied by the CHESSETUP system to satisfy the heating and domestic hot water demand is distributed as shown in Figure 9. As mentioned above, the system supplies 100 % of the thermal demand. Dark blue line corresponds to the monthly CHESSETUP system electrical consumption.

Figure 9: Corby's average Eco-home CHESSETUP system consumption and production

Analyzing in more detail the electrical Eco-home's behaviour, for the monitored period, the values presented in Figure 10 were registered in the control system. Blue sky line represents the total Eco-home's electrical consumption (Power demand), CHESSETUP system is about 39 % of the total electrical consumption in the period. The grey line represents the energy consumed from the electrical grid, and is about 41 % of the total electrical consumption in the period. Approximately 33 % of the electrical energy produced by the PV-T solar panels (yellow columns) is self-consumed by the Eco-homes; the rest of the surplus energy (green columns) is either discharged into the grid or storage in a small (5.5 kWh) in home battery.

Figure 10: Monthly Eco-homes average electrical performance

Figure 11 shows the average hourly Eco-homes electrical consumption (dark blue) and production (yellow) for different months (data corresponding to plot 45). The figure also shows the average hourly CHESS SETUP system electrical consumption for different months (orange). In these months it is observed that the electrical peak consumption occurs mainly in the first's hours and in the late afternoon coinciding with CHESS SETUP peak consumption. PV production supplies energy to the Eco-home and helps reduce the energy demand from the grid (dashed grey line) in the periods from 5:00 a.m. to 6:00 p.m. The green line corresponds to the electrical surplus, discharged to the grid. In June and July, the battery was not connected to the system. In August and September it is possible to observe how the battery takes advantage of the PV and the low cost of energy in the valley periods to charge, and provides energy to the house in the periods of greatest demand and low PV production. Similarly, it is worth mentioning that the battery provides energy in periods when the energy from the grid tends to have high carbon intensity.

Figure 11: Corby's Eco-home plot 45 average hourly electrical consumption and production for different months

Summarizing, the CHESSETUP system provides an annual estimated primary thermal energy savings of 7.000 kWh_{pci} (natural gas), 100 % of the Eco-homes thermal demand compared to the baseline case. An average annual electrical energy consumption of 6.300 kWh_e is estimated for the Eco-home, and an electrical energy production of 4.550 kWh_e, which would represent a 72 % saving of electrical energy consumption from the grid. This also represents an estimated energy cost saving of approximately 800 Euros per year per household, comparing the pilot with baseline case. Finally, it is also estimated a considerable saving in greenhouse gas emissions, close to 1,4 tCO₂/year, a reduction of 68 %

of the total Eco-home emissions compared to the baseline case (Figure 12). These values correspond to a house unit and should be scaled to the total houses number.

Figure 12: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions per Eco-home

If scaling to all pilot houses, there would be an estimated energy saving of 182 MWh per year of primary thermal energy compared with the baseline case. On the other hand, they would avoid about 35 tCO₂ yearly emissions.

To calculate the avoided CO₂ emissions, the methodology developed in the deliverable 'D4.3 Integration with the electrical system' has been used, where the emission factors of the electrical network were considered for the case of Corby (National Grid - Elexon, 2020) as well as the natural gas emission factors for the respective countries⁹. For a conservative estimation of the emissions avoided, the carbon footprint of PV panels is considered equal to 80 gCO₂/kWh (panels manufactured in economies dominated by coal).¹⁰

Although the monitoring of the system has not been possible for one-year period, data obtained from the period of June to September made it possible to know the system operation and their possible expected performance in cold seasons.

3.1.3.3. Seasonal thermal energy storage

Analysing the Earth Energy Bank behaviour for the monitored period, Figure 13 shows the monthly STES average temperature variation. Orange line represents the average monthly temperatures in the STES. Blue lines represent the average monthly outdoor temperature for the monitored period. It can be seen that, the STES temperatures are

⁹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/government-conversion-factors-for-company-reporting>

¹⁰ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/grantham-institute/public/publications/briefing-papers/Solar-power-for-CO2-mitigation---Grantham-BP-11.pdf>

always higher than the outside average temperatures. As this pilot uses a ground source heat pump (WSHP), the higher STES temperature comparing to the outside temperature helps to improve the performance of the heat pump, and consequently, the efficiency of the CHESSE SETUP system.

Figure 13: STES monthly average temperatures

The effect of and benefit from the seasonal accumulation would occur from the next cold season (autumn 2020 onward).

Figure 14 shows the soil temperature variation and the thermal contribution of the Earth Energy Bank for the period between June 24 and June 26, 2020. It is worth mentioning that these days the weather has varied between 12°C at night to 25°C at noon, and the weather has remained cloudy, partially cloudy, and rainy.

In Figure 14, yellow line (Sensor3_8m-mid-PT) presents soil temperature in the centre of EEB and 750 mm from the top of the EEB pile; orange line (Sensor2_8mC) shows soil temperature of the inner side of the EEB and 1,5 meters from top of the EEB pile; dark red line (Sensor1_6m) presents soil temperature 3 meters distance from the EEB (external) and 1,5 meters from top of the EEB pile. Sky blue line (ST prod) represents the PV-T thermal contribution to charge the EEB. Dashed green line (EEB thermal out) presents the EEB thermal contribution to the HP production, and finally, dark blue line (HP thermal prod) presents the HP thermal production.

In the same Figure 14, it can be seen how in the moments that the heat pump works (dark blue line different from 0), there is a significant heat contribution from the EEB (dashed green line). It can also be seen that with a certain delay, the temperature in the EEB (yellow line) decreases during the heat pump operation. Once the hybrid panels receive solar radiation (sky blue line), heat is transferred to the EEB through the heat transfer fluid, increasing the EEB temperature.

Figure 14: Plot 44 EEB temperatures variation for the period June 24th to 26th, 2020

3.1.3.4. Heat Pump performance

As already indicated in section '3.1.3.2 Energy savings', the CHESSETUP system was expected to supply 100 % of the Eco-home thermal demand.

Month	CHESSETUP energy consumption (kWh _e)	CHESSETUP heating production (kWh _t)	EER
Jun.	108,4	325,0	3,0
Jul.	108,7	312,3	2,9
Aug.	110,8	346,2	3,1
Sep.	122,8	356,1	2,9
Total	450,7	1.339,6	3,0

Table 4: CHESSETUP heat pump energy performance

Table 4 shows the electrical energy consumption and thermal production values of the CHESSETUP system for the period June to September 2020. It should be taken into consideration that the considered electrical energy consumption also includes the electrical consumption of auxiliaries' equipment such as hydraulic pumps, control and monitoring system. Therefore, the energy efficiency ratio (EER) obtained for each month is the coefficient corresponding to the CHESSETUP system, including the heat pump. The average EER for the monitored period would be 3,0.

Figure 15: Outside Average temperature vs CHESSETUP system average monthly EER shows CHESSETUP system averages monthly EERs for the period and

the average monthly outdoor temperatures and the STES average temperature for the monitored period.

Figure 15: Outside Average temperature vs CHESSE SETUP system average monthly EER

Analysing the behaviour of the system for one year period (Table 10), the estimated EER of the CHESSE SETUP system for the Eco-homes would be 2,6; value slightly lower than the ERR 3,0 estimated in deliverable 3.7 (Table 2).

Something that must be taken into account is that the data shown correspond to the average of the data obtained from all the monitored dwellings. Therefore, if each home is analysed individually, there are cases in which the performance of the CHESSE SETUP system (heat pump) is above the estimate. In other cases, such as plot 44 (demo-site), the performance is slightly lower than expected. This is because the performance of the system is linked to the inhabitants' patterns of use or comfort conditions.

3.1.4. Corby's dwelling CHESSE SETUP system implementation impact

The CHESSE SETUP system implemented in Corby is a prototype for a residential building, replicated in 26 different homes.

The initial system configuration has been adapted to the different buildings typologies. The final solution uses photovoltaic and hybrid solar panels, storing the thermal energy production in the earth energy bank, and part of the surplus electricity production in batteries. A geothermal heat pump is used to recover the stored thermal energy and to meet the demands of heating as well as DHW.

Due to the confinement, the moves of the new inhabitants have been delayed. Furthermore, in the case of already inhabited dwellings, given that most of the

inhabitants are teleworking, the buildings currently do not function as they were initially expected. Thus, this COVID-19 pandemic period also affected the operation of the system, increasing heating demand and DHW consumption. However, once we hit the new normal, some of the next steps have already been identified to further improve energy efficiency and cost savings as follows:

- Revise the operation schedules for the new normal according the building capacity, the comfort temperatures and the operating hours of the users.
- Optimize the heap pump shut down to reduce the peak consumption.

Table 5 summarizes the results of the implementation of the CHESSE SETUP system in the aforementioned pilot. The column 'Simulated' presents the values obtained as results of comparing the baseline case (natural gas boiler) with the system simulated in 'D3.7 Pilot experience report'. The column 'Monitored' presents the values obtained as a result of comparing the system operation (2019-2020) of the implemented system with the base line (natural gas boiler).

		Simulated	Monitored
Demands			
Heating and DHW Cons. (kWh _t /year)		6.188	6.300
Other electric cons. (kWh _e /year)		3.412	3.013
Configuration			
Total sqm (m ²)		167.1	167.1
Solar Panels surface (m ²)		32	32
Solar Panels Peak power (kWp)		5,00	5,00
STES Vol (m ³)		140	140
HP Cons. (kWh _e /year)		1.800	2.440
EER		3,0	2,6
Operation			
PV-T / PV production	Electrical (kWh _e /year)	4.269	4.553
	Thermal (kWh/year)	4.229	4.743
STES temp. ¹¹	Min (°C)	2	20,1
	Max (°C)	17	22,4
	Average (°C)	9	-
Buffer temp.(°C)		27	55
Backup cons. (kWh _{pci} /year)		-	-
Savings			
Natural Gas	(kWh _{pci} /year)	6.876	7.000
	(%)	100%	100%
Electricity	(kWh _e /year)	-2.045	-2.440
	(%)	-59,9%	-56,9%
Total energy	(kWh/year)	4.876	4.560
	(%)	47,2%	45,6%

¹¹ The 'Monitored' column considers the period from April to September 2020.

CO ₂	(kgCO ₂ /yr)	1.841	1.354
	(%)	85,8%	67,7%

Table 5: Results of the CHESSE SETUP system implementation for Corby's dwellings pilot experience

The CHESSE SETUP system provides an annual estimated gas consumption savings of 7.000 kWh_{pci}, 100 % of the Eco-home thermal demand compared to the baseline case. On the other hand, each Eco-home presents an increase in electricity consumption compared to the baseline case of 2.440 kWh_e. The system represents a reduction of 45,6 % of the total energy consumption, and a reduction of 67,7 % of the greenhouse gases emissions (1,4 tCO₂/yr).

3.2. Lavola Ecobuilding pilot experience

3.2.1 CHESSE SETUP system implemented

The CHESSE SETUP system implemented in Lavola's Ecobuilding consists of a prototype for an office building. As mentioned in D5.1, this pilot experience was conditioned in terms of space availability given the space limitation of the site and the building, resulting in a reduced space for the thermal energy storage tank. After studying different options (i.e. CHESSE SETUP system configurations) for the location of the thermal storage tank, its operability with the solar panels and heat pump, the energy savings and the investment, Lavola finally opted for CHESSE SETUP 'version 3.0' as the most suitable for the pilot. Table 6 shows three different CHESSE SETUP system configurations proposed.

SYSTEM CONFIGURATION		CHESSE SETUP 1.0	CHESSE SETUP 2.0	CHESSE SETUP 3.0
Elements and equipment description	Renewal energy	PV-T panels: 56 m ² at 15 % electrical and 45 % thermal efficiencies.	PV panels: 56 m ² at 15 % electrical efficiency, equivalent to 9,6 kWp.	PV panels: 58 m ² at 17 % electrical efficiency, equivalent to 9,9 kWp.
	Energy storage	Thermal storage: 3,8 m ³ water tank located in the garage Thermal capacity: 119 kWh _t	Thermal storage: 3,8 m ³ water tank located in the garage Thermal capacity: 119 kWh _t	Thermal storage: 33 m ³ slab of the whole building Thermal capacity: 400 kWh _t
	Heat Pump	Carrier WSHP: 40 kW _t (5,7 kW _e , COP of 7,05), fed by the tank to serve the heating needs of 3 rd Floor.	Airlan ASHP: 18,5 kW _t (4,36 kW _t , COP 4,2) to heat up the storage tank. Carrier WSHP ¹ : 40 kW _t (5,7 kW _e , COP of 7,05), fed by the tank to serve the heating needs of 3 rd Floor.	Carrier ASHP: 60 kW _t to serve the heating needs of the whole building.
	Buffer tank	Buffer tank: 300 l	Buffer tank: 300 l	Buffer tank: 300 l
	Backup	Natural gas boiler: existing boiler	Natural gas boiler: existing boiler	Natural gas boiler: existing boiler
Predicted System performance ¹²	System coverage	3 rd Floor	3 rd Floor	Entire Building
	Wasted heat energy produced by panels (%)	>75 %	0 %	0%
	Heating energy savings (%)	9 %	15 %	32%

¹² The predicted system performance figures are referred to the total building energy consumption.

Electricity energy savings (%)	11 %	14 %	14%
Total energy saving (%)	11%	16%	22%
Total cost savings (%)	11%	15%	18%
Total CO2 emissions saving (%)	11%	15%	20%

Table 6: Different CHESSE SETUP system configurations proposed for Lavola's Ecobuilding

Figure 16 shows the scheme of the CHESSE SETUP system implemented in Lavola's Ecobuilding. The main elements are represented: solar photovoltaic panels, air source heat pump, buffer tank, back-up boiler and the radiating floor.

Figure 16: Lavola's Ecobuilding schematic CHESSE SETUP system

Table 7 summarizes the main components used for the implementation of CHESSE SETUP system; these components have been described in 'D5.1 Construction Plan Report'.

System components	Characteristics
Photovoltaic panels	Jinko JKM3300PP-72 (17% electric efficiency) 9,9 kWp 58 m ² 30 panels Slope 0°
Air-source heat pump	Carrier 30RQS-060B ¹³ Heating Power 61 kW (SCOP 3,07) Cooling Power 59 kW (ESERR 3,61)
Buffer tank	300 litres 40 °C- 45 °C heating set-point temperature 12 °C - 7 °C cooling set-point temperature
Thermal Storage	33 m ³ thermal mass taking advantage of the building slab upper layer of mortar where radiant floor heating is already installed.
Natural gas boiler (existing)	168 kW

Table 7: Lavola's Ecobuilding CHESSE SETUP system components

3.2.2. Data collection periods

The beginning of the period studied depended on the monitoring and control system start-up date and the system commissioning end date. For Lavola pilot's the monitoring system started collecting PV energy generation data since September 2018. The heat pump was commissioned on July 2019, and the system commissioning ended in September 2019.

It should be noted that the control system worked automatically from July 2019 until now, but at the middle of March, the activities of the office were suspended due to COVID-19 and the thermal demand of the system decreased to the minimum. Throughout the period from July 2019 to March 2020, all heating and cooling demands were covered by CHESSE SETUP system; there was no thermal input from gas the boiler or the chiller. Therefore, in Lavola's Ecobuilding pilot, the CHESSE SETUP system has been operational from July 2019 to March 2020.

Due to the above, the analysis of the system data is carried out in two stages. First, CHESSE SETUP system performance is analysed in the period from August 2019 to March 2020, with real values obtained from the pilot monitoring. Secondly, BCN has performed a deep analysis on relevant data coming from the monitoring & control system deployed by WAT, which provided relevant information from August 2019 until March 2020: therefore, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation,

¹³ https://www.ahi-carrier.gr/en/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2017/06/PSD-30RBS_30RQS_039_160-1.pdf

historical energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

3.2.3. CHESSE SETUP system operation and performance

3.2.3.1. Building energy consumption

As mentioned in deliverable 'D5.1 Construction plan report', initially the heating thermal demand of the Ecobuilding was considered to be supplied only by the CHESSE SETUP system. Table 8 shows information corresponding to both thermal and electrical energy demand from Lavola Ecobuilding regarding weather conditions over the year (i.e. seasonality) and occupancy profiles during 2016.

Month	Heating demand (kWh _t)	Cooling demand (kWh _t)	Natural Gas consumption (kWh _{PCI})	Chiller consumption (kWh _e)	Total electricity consumption (kWh _e)
Apr.	2.108	2.133	2.007	900	5.741
May	0	4.740	0	2.000	5.479
Jun.	0	5.925	0	2.500	5.141
Jul.	0	7.110	0	3.000	7.415
Aug.	0	5.451	0	2.300	6.184
Sept	0	4.503	0	1.900	6.369
Oct.	1.599	2.844	1.522	1.200	5.196
Nov.	10.345	90	9.852	38	5.256
Dec.	16.682	2.038	15.888	860	5.410
Jan.	16.870	948	16.067	400	7.052
Feb.	11.021	592	10.469	250	6.493
Mar.	7.876	1.896	7.501	800	6.258
TOTAL	66.501	38.270	63.334	16.148	71.994

Table 8: Energy demand of Lavola's Ecobuilding. Source: Deliverable 3.7

These figures were used in 'D3.7 Pilot experience report' and 'D5.1 Construction plan report' to carry out the simulation and dimensioning of the CHESSE SETUP system, as they are considered representative thermal demands of the Ecobuilding heating system.

Table 9 shows the energy and thermal demands corresponding to the period 2019-2020. As mentioned above, in September 2019 the commissioning of the system was carried out. From there the control system was programmed to work automatically, managing thermal production and meeting demands intelligently.

The grey rows come from an estimation performed by LVL and BCN taking into account the most recent energy bills, heating and cooling degree days, and from the monitoring

and control systems. This issue was reported in 'D1.2 Project progress report' and it is detailed again in Annex, it is due to a failure of the calorimeter installed at the outlet of the heat pump.

Month	Heating demand (kWh _t)	Cooling demand (kWh _t)	CHESSE SETUP cons. (kWh _e)	Other Elect. Cons. (kWh _e)	PV Elect. gen. (kWh _e)	Elect. cons. from GRID (kWh _e)	Total El. Cons. (kWh _e)
Apr.	5.696	0	1.328	2.889	976	3.241	4.217
May	1.884	0	614	3.048	1.093	2.569	3.662
Jun.	0	4.006	1.305	3.174	1.375	3.104	4.479
Jul.	0	6.233	2.030	3.307	1.472	3.865	5.337
Aug.	0	3.962	821	5.658	1.513	4.967	6.480
Sept	0	4.382	1.012	5.106	1194	4.924	6.118
Oct.	3.322	1.390	1.014	4.340	768	4.595	5.363
Nov.	10.946	0	4.407	5.148	433	9.122	9.555
Dec.	12.097	0	5.922	4.473	332	10.063	10.395
Jan.	14.326	0	7.361	5.486	413	12.434	12.847
Feb.	9.579	0	4.067	4.591	685	7.973	8.658
Mar.	9.292	0	3.541	3.969	805	6.705	7.510
TOTAL	67.142	19.972	33.424	51.196	11.058	73.562	84.620

Table 9: Monitored energy demand Lavola's Ecobuilding 2019-2020

Comparing Table 8 and Table 9, the heating thermal demand observed on the Ecobuilding for a yearly period is quite the same. In addition, it should be noted that the cooling demand has decreased by almost 50%.

Figure 17 shows the difference between both period thermal demands. Comparing the heating demand, it is observed a little reduction during the winter with respect to 2016, not so for March, April and May where the heating demand is higher than in the respective months of 2016. On the other hand, the cooling demand is lower throughout the monitored period than that corresponding to 2016.

Figure 17: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored

As mentioned in the deliverable D5.1, it should be remembered that the proposed CHESSE SETUP system was initially sized to supply only the heating thermal demand for the entire building. In the final design phase of the CHESSE SETUP system, it has been decided to introduce the cooling demand. In this sense, the system was initially projected to supply 66.501 kWh_t, but finally the system will supply 87.113 kWh_t.

3.2.3.2. Energy savings

The main feature of this reference case is the thermal savings that can be provided through the maximal exploitation of the ASHP while matching, as much as possible, its consumption curve with PV generation curve.

The system studied combines electrical generation coming from the photovoltaic panels and the use of a high-efficiency air-water heat pump. The total Lavola's Ecobuilding energy savings has been estimated in Table 10. It can be seen the data registered during the period of September 2019 to March 2020, and the estimated values for the period of April to August (in grey). The 'Baseline' case was also studied, where all the Ecobuilding thermal demand is supposed to be covered by the gas boiler and the chiller.

D5.4 Monitoring results report

Lavola's Ecobuilding																	
CHESSE SETUP system									Baseline								
Month	Heating					Building			Heating					Building			
	Heating (kWh _t)	Cooling (kWh _t)	Total Thermal Out. (kWh _t)	EER	Energy Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)	Energy Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)	Boiler savings (kWh _{PEL})	Energy cost (€)	Chiller savings (kWh _e)	Energy cost (€)	Total Energy (kWh)	Energy Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)	Energy Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)
Apr.	5.695,8	0	5.695,8	4,29	59,43	127,3	547,66	531,1	6.732,6	430,03	0	0,00	6.732,6	430,03	1.771,4	918,26	2.175,3
May	1.884,0	0	1.884,0	3,07	81,06	20,4	434,04	446,5	2.227,0	142,24	0	0,00	2.227,0	142,24	585,9	657,34	1.012,0
Jun.	0	4.006,0	4.006,0	3,07	11,81	100,2	524,56	543,9	0	0	1.691,7	285,86	1.691,7	285,86	236,5	822,23	680,2
Jul.	0	6.233,0	6.233,0	3,07	94,42	195,8	653,11	658,0	0	0	2.632,2	444,78	2.632,2	444,78	367,9	1.003,47	830,1
Aug.	0	3.961,7	3.961,7	4,82	116,83	24,4	839,32	815,3	0	0	1.673,0	282,70	1.673,0	282,70	233,9	1.238,85	1.024,8
Sept.	0	4.381,6	4.381,6	4,33	-30,7	70,1	832,06	783,4	0	0	1.850,3	312,67	1.850,3	312,67	258,6	1.175,42	972,3
Oct.	3.322,4	1.389,6	4.712,0	4,64	41,79	96,0	776,46	703,7	3.927,2	250,84	586,8	99,16	4.514,0	350	1115,3	1.084,67	1.723,0
Nov.	10.945,9	0	10.945,9	2,48	671,58	590,16	1.541,42	1309,70	12.938,5	826,42	0,00	0,00	12.938,5	826,42	3.404,3	1.696,27	4.123,8
Dec.	12.096,7	0	12.096,7	2,04	944,60	807,96	1.700,43	1433,20	14.298,7	913,30	0,00	0,00	14.298,7	913,30	3.762,2	1.669,14	4.387,4
Jan.	14.326,2	0	14.326,2	1,95	1.174,08	1004,24	2.101,08	1771,06	16.934,0	1.081,63	0,00	0,00	16.934,0	1.081,63	4.455,6	2.008,63	5.222,4
Feb.	9.579,5	0	9.579,5	2,36	571,56	527,58	1.347,27	1169,25	11.323,2	723,25	0,00	0,00	11.323,2	723,25	2.979,3	1.498,96	3.621,0
Mar.	9.291,8	0	9.291,8	2,62	462,21	446,78	1.133,00	1001,66	10.983,2	701,53	0,00	0,00	10.983,2	701,53	2.889,8	1.372,33	3.444,7
TOTAL	67.142,2	19.971,8	87.113,9		3.779,26	4010,90	12.430,41	11167,18	79.364,3	5.069,25	8.434,0	1.425,17	87.798,4	6.494,42	22.060,7	15.145,57	29.217,0

Table 10: Comparative table between CHESSE SETUP thermal energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Lavola's pilot

As mentioned previously, both heating and cooling demand are now entirely supplied by the CHESSE SETUP system (PV with ASHP). This provides 79.364 kWh_{PCI} estimated primary thermal energy savings, as it is the amount of natural gas that has been estimated to be saved as thermal energy of Ecobuilding's heating demand previously satisfied with natural gas combustion at the existing boiler.

Figure 18 shows the relationship between the photovoltaic production, the CHESSE SETUP system electrical consumption, and the heating and cooling thermal demands for each month. It should be noted that not all the energy produced by the photovoltaic panels is consumed by the CHESSE SETUP system, the surplus is self-consumed by the Ecobuilding.

Figure 18: PV production, Ecobuilding energy demand, and CHESSE SETUP system energy consumption

As shown in Table 9 and Table 10, for the period of one year, the estimated total electrical consumption of the CHESSE SETUP system is 33.424 kWh_e. This consumption is divided in two different sources: 11.058 kWh_e/year comes from the PV panels' production and 22.365 kWh_e/year comes from the grid. In those months with greatest solar radiation (spring-summer), there is a surplus of PV production compared to the consumption of the system, being July the exception due to high refrigeration demand. In months with less solar radiation, photovoltaic production covers between 6% and 15% of the CHESSE SETUP consumption.

Figure 19 shows the average daily CHESSE SETUP system electrical production and consumption for different months. In cold months it is observed that the peak of the system's energy consumption (red) occurs in the early hours of the day. PV production (yellow) supplies energy to the system and helps reduce the demand for energy from the grid (grey) in the periods from 8:00 a.m. to 6:00 p.m. It should be remembered

that in months of high radiation, the entire electrical surplus produced by the PV panels (green) is self-consumed by the Ecobuilding. It is also observed that in months with mild weather, the energy demand of the system is distributed more evenly throughout the day.

Figure 19: CHESSE SETUP average daily electrical consumption and production for different months

Summarizing, the CHESSE SETUP system provides an annual estimated gas consumption savings of 79.364 kWh_{pci}, 100 % of the Ecobuilding primary energy thermal demand compared to the baseline case. On the other hand, the Ecobuilding presents an increase in annual estimated electricity consumption of 33.424 kWh_e compared to the baseline case. This increase in electricity consumption must be subtracted from the estimated production of photovoltaic energy (11.058 kWh_e), and the savings in electricity consumption of the chiller used in the baseline case (8.434 kWh_e). Therefore, the Ecobuilding as a whole presents an increase in electricity consumption compared to the baseline case of 13.930 kWh_e per year (Figure 20). This also represents an estimated energy cost saving of approximately 2.700 Euros per year for the building,

comparing the pilot with the baseline case. Finally, it is also estimated a considerable saving in greenhouse gas emissions, close to 18 tCO₂/year, a reduction of 61 % of the total Ecobuilding emissions compared to the baseline case (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions

In deliverables D3.7 and D5.1, after carried out the simulations and data analysis of the CHES-SETUP system performance, a total energy saving of 14% for electricity and 46% for Natural Gas were expected to obtain for this pilot. In addition, for the Ecobuilding was estimated 35% of greenhouse gas emission savings.

To calculate the avoided CO₂ emissions, the methodology developed in the deliverable 'D4.3 Integration with the electrical system' has been used, where the emission factors of the electrical network were considered for the case of Lavola pilot (Red Eléctrica de España SA, 2020), as well as the natural gas emission factors for the respective countries¹⁴. For a conservative estimation of the emissions avoided, the carbon footprint of PV panels is considered equal to 80 gCO₂/kWh (panels manufactured in economies dominated by coal).¹⁵

Although the monitoring of the system has not been possible for one year period, the data obtained from the period of August to March made it possible to know in detail the system operation and their expected performance in cold periods (autumn and winter).

The results obtained from the monitoring period are widely superior to those calculated in deliverables D3.7 and D5.1. This mainly due to the fact that 100% of the heating demand has been covered with the CHES-SETUP system instead of using the boiler, as well as 100% of the cooling demand was supplied by the system instead of using the

¹⁴ https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/factores_emision_tcm30-479095.pdf

¹⁵ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/grantham-institute/public/publications/briefing-papers/Solar-power-for-CO2-mitigation---Grantham-BP-11.pdf>

chiller. This, results in an estimated emission reduction higher than that obtained in the D5.1.

The deliverable D6.1 presents an analysis of the economic savings generated by the CHESSE SETUP system for each pilot. This analysis is performed based on the energy, thermal and electrical savings, presented in this document.

3.2.3.3. Heat Pump performance

As already indicated in section '3.2.3.2 Energy savings', the CHESSE SETUP system supplied 100% of the Lavola's Ecobuilding thermal demand in the period from August 2019 to March 2020.

Table 11 shows the electrical energy consumption and thermal production values of the CHESSE SETUP system. It should be taken into consideration that the considered electrical energy consumption also includes the electrical consumption of auxiliaries' equipment such as hydraulic pumps, control and monitoring system. Therefore, the energy efficiency ratio (EER) obtained for each month is the coefficient corresponding to the CHESSE SETUP system, including the heat pump. Figure 21 shows CHESSE SETUP system averages monthly EERs for the monitored period and the average monthly outdoor temperatures for the monitored period.

Month	CHESSE SETUP energy consumption (kWh _e)	CHESSE SETUP heating production (kWh _t)	CHESSE SETUP cooling production (kWh _t)	EER
Aug.	821,38		3.961,65	4,82
Sep.	1.012,00		4.381,59	4,33
Oct.	1.014,83	3.322,41	1.389,57	4,64
Nov.	4.407,14	10.945,94		2,48
Dec.	5.922,36	12.096,67		2,04
Jan.	7.361,04	14.326,19		1,95
Feb.	4.067,21	9.579,46		2,36
Mar.	3.540,77	9.291,78		2,62
Total	28.146,73	59.562,45	9.732,81	2,46

Table 11: CHESSE SETUP heat pump energy performance

As shown in Table 10 and Figure 18, January was the month with the highest thermal demand. Similarly, Figure 21 shows that January has been the month with the lowest temperatures, being the average ambient temperature 4,3 °C, and the minimum temperature registered -3,7 °C.

Figure 21: Lavola's Ecobuilding outdoor average monthly temperatures

In January the CHESSE SETUP system supplied 14.326 kWh_t (Table 11), with an average EER of 1,95 (Figure 22). On the other hand, analysing the cooling demands, it is observed that September was the month with the highest demand, 4.381,6 kWh_t and the CHESSE SETUP system presented an EER of 4,3. It is worth mentioning that Lavola's offices are closed for a period of 15 days during the month of August for holidays.

Figure 22: Outside Average temperature vs CHESSE SETUP system average monthly EER and COP

The technical justification is that the decrease in the EER according to the increase in the condensation temperature does not depend on the energy source (air, water or soil) but that the temperature does have an impact on the performance of the heat pump: provided that the working temperature of the fluid is lower. It will facilitate the condensation of the refrigerant, thus increasing the EER and the thermal power supplied by the heat pump.

3.2.3.4. Seasonal thermal energy storage

D3.7 mentioned that Lavola is working on the transformation of the building into a Nearly Zero Energy Building (nZEB). Lavola's Ecobuilding renewed their LEED Gold certification for Existing Buildings¹⁶ in 2015. The energy needs of the building are reduced a lot thanks to good architecture and its civil engineering design.

From now, the primary energy consumption of the building is also reduced a lot due to the application of an integrated efficient heating and cooling system, including the solar PV system, the air-water heat pump and the monitoring and control system.

Increasing the thermal insulation of walls and roofs considerably lengthens the time interval when the temperature inside a building remains comfortable after the heating has been switched off. This means that well-insulated buildings offer the necessary flexibility to receive energy when it is available, attenuating the peaks in power demand on the electricity grid (when all inefficient buildings demand power) and properly exploiting moments of overabundance and scarcity of the supply of energy from renewable sources.

The report developed by the 'Politecnico de Milano' (Pagliano, Armani, Erba, & Sangalli, 2020) studied the relation between the building thermal insulation and the capacity of extending the time interval during which a building will maintain indoor conditions in the comfort range. The main objectives of the study were:

- *Match the demand with the supply of local energy* by removing the current rigidity of energy demand from buildings and thus allow them to “ask for” energy precisely when it is available from local sources (renewable or recovered energy) or to exchange energy with other buildings in a flexible way.
- *Exploit moments of an overabundance of renewable energy supply on the grid by making available energy storage capabilities* (in the form of the thermal capacity of the building fabric) when such moments occur.
- *Manage conditions of energy supply shortage by attenuating peak power demand on the grid* (peak shaving, demand response, potential participation in the capacity market creating added value additionally to the value linked with energy savings and increased comfort).

In the case of Lavola Ecobuilding, a similar study should be developed, in which to analyze how long the building can maintain comfort conditions after the heating or cooling system has been turned off. The objective will be to test if the energy storage potential embedded in the mass of the building fabric can have a positive effect on the energy system as a whole. The study mentioned above is outside the scope of this project but it is highly recommended as a future stage.

¹⁶ <https://www.usgbc.org/leed/rating-systems/existing-buildings>

3.2.4. Lavola's CHESSE SETUP system implementation impact

The CHESSE SETUP system implemented in Lavola's Ecobuilding is a small scale prototype for an office building.

The initial system configuration had to be modified to adapt to the circumstances of the existing building. In order to accomplish the goals of the CHESSE-SETUP system implementation in the Ecobuilding, and after studying the challenges and constraints (different possibilities for the location of the thermal storage tank and its operability with the solar-hybrid panels and water source heat pump) a variation has been build and it represents a show case for existing buildings with lack of space for thermal storage and renewable technology potential. The system also includes the cooling demand.

The final solution maintains the photovoltaic panels as the energy production side of the system that feeds an efficient air source heat pump to heat the thermal storage, which in this case is the thermal mass of the building slab upper layer of mortar where the radiant floor heating is already installed.

PV array was commissioned in September 2018 and the heat pump in June 2019. The whole CHESSE SETUP system has been operational from July 2019 to March 2020. However, at the middle of March, the activities of the office were suspended due to COVID-19 and the thermal demand of the system decreased to the minimum.

During the lockdown the building was closed and after it, it is only open with the 30% maximum of the capacity. Given that most of the users of the office are teleworking, the building at the present still does not work as it will use to do. Thus, this pandemic period of the COVID-19 also affected the operations of the system. However, once we get to the new normal some of next steps are already been identified to keep improving the energy efficiency and cost savings as follows:

- Revise the operation schedules for the new normal according the building capacity, the comfort temperatures and the operating hours of the users.
- Optimize the heap pump shut down to reduce the peak consumption.
- Analyze to use the range of 32 °C - 35 °C of the heat pump, instead of the 40 °C - 45 °C used nowadays in the winter period.
- Adjust the heap pump operation according to the tariff periods of the electricity company, to reduce the electricity costs. As well analyze the demand curves of the electrical market to reduce the emissions.
- Analyze of how long the building can maintain the comfort conditions when the system is turn off.

Table 12 summarizes the results of the implementation of the CHESSE SETUP system in the aforementioned pilot. The column 'Simulated' presents the values obtained as

results of comparing the baseline case (2016) with the system simulated in the 'D3.7 Pilot experience report'. The column 'Monitored' presents the values obtained as a result of comparing the system operation (2019-2020) of the implemented system with the base line (natural gas boiler).

		Simulated	Monitored
Demands			
Heating and DHW Cons. (kWh _t /year)		66.504	67.142
Cooling (kWh _t /year)		38.271	19.972
Other electric cons. (kWh _e /year)		71.995	51.197
Configuration			
Total sqm (m ²)		827	827
Solar Panels surface (m ²)		56	56
Solar Panels Peak power (kWp)		9,66	9,66
STES Vol. (m ³)		33	33
HP Cons. (kWh _e /year)		15.211	33.424
COP* - EER		5,00*	2,46
Operation			
PV production	Electrical (kWh _e /year)	14.608	11.058
STES temp.	Min (°C)	27	-
	Max (°C)	32	-
	Average (°C)	29	-
Buffer temp.(°C)		27	40-45 / 12-7
Backup cons. (kWh _{pci} /year)		0	0
Savings			
Natural Gas	(kWh _{pci} /year)	63.337	79.364
	(%)	100%	100%
Electricity	(kWh _e /year)	-603	-13.930
	(%)	-0,8%	-23,4%
Total energy	(kWh/year)	62.734	65.434
	(%)	46,4%	47,1%
CO ₂	(kgCO ₂ /yr)	16.580	17.671
	(%)	62,0%	61,0%

Table 12: Simulated vs monitored CHESS SETUP system implementation impacts for Lavola's Ecobuilding

The CHESS SETUP system provides an annual estimated gas consumption savings of 79.364 kWh_{pci}, 100 % of the Ecobuilding thermal demand compared to the baseline case. On the other hand, the Ecobuilding as a whole presents an increase in electricity consumption compared to the baseline case of 13.930 kWh_e (due to the electricity consumption of 33.424 kWh_e of the heat pump, less the savings from the production of photovoltaic energy, 11.058 kWh_e, and the savings in electricity consumption of the existing chiller 8.434 kWh_e). The system represents a reduction of 47 % of the total energy consumption, and a reduction of 61 % of the greenhouse gases emissions (17,6 tCO₂/yr).

3.3. Sports Centre (Eurofitness) Sant Cugat pilot experience

3.3.1. CHESS SETUP system implemented

The CHESS SETUP system implementation in the Eurofitness building is conditioned in terms of space availability dimensions of the areas to be conditioned and elevated heating and DHW consumptions. After studying different possibilities for the location of the thermal storage tank and its operability with the solar-hybrid panels and heat pump, and with the aim of optimizing the system, the CHESS SETUP system was designed to cover the 'swimming-pool water' heat demand.

Figure 23 shows the scheme of the CHESS SETUP system implemented in Sant Cugat's Sports Centre. The main elements are represented: solar hybrid panels, seasonal thermal energy storage tank, heat pump, buffer tank, back-up boiler and swimming-pool (thermal demand).

Figure 23: Sant Cugat's Sports Centre schematic CHESS SETUP system

Table 13 summarizes the main components used for the implementation of CHESS SETUP system; these components have been described in 'D5.1 Construction Plan Report'.

System components	Characteristics
Hybrid panels	Abora AH-60 SK (59% thermal efficiency, 16% electric efficiency) 41,6 kWp 264 m ² 160 panels Slope 25°
Seasonal Thermal Storage Tank	100 m ³ steel water tank 60 °C set-point temperature
Water-water heat pump	Carrier 61WG-o60 Heat Power 97,5 kW COP _H 5,6
Buffer tank (existing)	1000 litres 45 °C set-point temperature
Natural gas boiler (existing)	2 boilers of 550 kW

Table 13: Sant Cugat's CHESS SETUP system components.

3.3.2. Data collection periods

The beginning of the period studied depends on monitoring and control system start-up date and the system commissioning end date. For Sant Cugat pilot's the monitoring system started collecting data at the beginning of September 2019, and the system commissioning ended in the middle of September, so the data analysis period began in September 2019.

It should be noted that the control system was working automatically until the end of March 2020. Due to COVID-19 the activities of the sports centre were suspended and the CHESS SETUP system was turned off. Therefore, in Sant Cugat pilot, the CHESS SETUP system has been operational from September 2019 to March 2020.

Due to the above, the analysis of the system data is carried out in two stages. First, the CHESS SETUP system performance is analyzed in the period September 2019 to March 2020, with real values obtained from the pilot monitoring. Secondly, BCN has performed a deep analysis on relevant data coming from the monitoring & control system deployed by WAT, which provided relevant information from September 2019 until March 2020: therefore, the rest of the year's system performance has been forecasted taking into account the geographical demonstration site location, solar irradiation, historical energy bills and expected system performance under standard climatological conditions of each season.

Last but not least, it should be noted that the fluid (water) of the seasonal thermal energy storage, at the beginning of the operation period (September), was at 24 °C degrees, very similar to the network water supply temperature. The system was not accumulating thermal energy in the months of greatest radiation (summer), therefore it is considered that the system could not provide the benefits of seasonal thermal

accumulation during the first cold period. In any case, the benefits of STES will be observed in shorter periods of time.

3.3.3. CHESSE SETUP system operation and performance

3.3.3.1. Building energy consumption

As mentioned in the deliverable 'D3.7 Pilot's experience report', the thermal energy demand of the Sports Centre building is divided in three different uses: Swimming-pool Water, Swimming-pool Air Treatment, and Domestic Hot Water. Swimming-pool Air Treatment consumption is the most important, it represents 45 % of whole consumption while the remaining 55 % is split into similar amount for the other uses (Swimming-pool water 28 % and DHW 27 %). Table 14 shows information corresponding to both thermal and electrical energy demands from Sant Cugat's Sports Centre regarding weather conditions during the year (i.e. seasonality) and occupancy profiles from 2016.

Month	Swimming-pool water heating (kWh _t)	Swimming-pool Air treatment (kWh _t)	Domestic Hot Water (kWh _t)	Total thermal demand (kWh _t)	Electricity consumption (kWh _e)
Apr.	39.056	63.980	37.082	140.119	88.130
May	39.515	44.290	33.958	117.763	81.190
Jun.	22.248	25.949	23.195	71.393	78.951
Jul.	22.132	12.615	12.887	47.635	88.987
Aug.	22.990	23.667	9.023	55.681	86.647
Sep.	23.078	39.399	23.286	85.763	96.235
Oct.	40.358	57.348	34.834	132.541	101.210
Nov.	40.689	72.029	40.378	153.096	98.271
Dec.	44.576	84.820	52.024	181.420	89.634
Jan.	44.576	95.692	52.024	192.292	92.683
Feb.	39.501	86.006	40.758	166.265	78.501
Mar.	42.046	76.642	41.725	160.413	65.467
TOTAL	420.765	682.443	401.178	1.504.387	1.045.906

Table 14: Energy demand of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre. Source: Deliverable 3.7

These figures were used in 'D3.7 Pilot experience report' and 'D5.1 Construction plan report' to carry out the simulation and dimensioning of the CHESSE SETUP system, as they are considered representative thermal demands of the Sports Centre heating system.

Table 15 shows the thermal demands corresponding to the period 2019-2020. In September 2019 the commissioning of the system was carried out. From there the control system was programmed to work automatically, managing thermal production and meeting demands intelligently.

Month	Swimming-pool water heating (kWh _t)	Swimming-pool Air treatment (kWh _t)	Domestic Hot Water (kWh _t)	Total thermal demand (kWh _t)
Apr.	60.894	99.756	57.818	218.469
May	58.606	65.689	50.365	174.661
Jun.	28.835	33.633	30.064	92.533
Jul.	28.996	16.528	16.885	62.410
Aug.	26.034	26.801	10.218	63.053
Sep.	48.611	43.591	25.763	117.967
Oct.	67.063	77.250	46.923	191.236
Nov.	49.873	68.992	38.675	157.541
Dec.	74.299	124.064	76.094	274.458
Jan.	81.707	160.162	87.074	328.944
Feb.	54.649	93.732	44.419	192.801
Mar.	54.875	100.028	54.457	209.361
TOTAL	630.753	910.232	538.758	2.075.485

Table 15: Monitored thermal demand Sant Cugat's Sports Centre 2019-2020

Comparing Table 14 and Table 15, a total thermal demand increase of 38 % is observed on the Sports Centre for a yearly period. As mentioned in the deliverables D3.7 and D5.1, it should be remembered that the proposed CHESSE SETUP system was projected to supply thermal demand for the 'swimming-pool water'. In this sense, comparing the 'Swimming-pool water' demands figures on both tables, a 33 % increase is observed for the same period studied.

Figure 24 shows that the increase in the total energy demand, comparing both periods, is mainly due to the thermal demand of December and January. In the same figure, it is also observed that the 'Swimming-pool water' thermal demand also presents an increase for the same period.

Figure 24: Thermal demand comparisons 2016 vs monitored period

The proposed CHESSE SETUP system has been sized to supply heat to the “Swimming-pool water” load, which corresponds to 30 % of the building's total thermal demand. Therefore, the analysis results will focus on the system performance to satisfy this demand.

3.3.3.2. Energy savings

The system studied combines thermal generation coming from the hybrid PV-T panels and sensible heat storage performed in the thermal energy storage in the form of a 100 m³ water tank, and the use of a high-efficiency heat pump. The total Sports Centre energy savings has been estimated in Table 16. It shows data registered during the period of September 2019 to March 2020, and the estimated values for the period of April to August (in grey). The ‘Baseline’ case was also studied, where all Sports Centre thermal demand is supposed to be covered only by the gas boiler system installed.

The grey rows come from an estimation performed taking into account the most recent energy bills and monitoring and control system’s data before the current COVID-19 emergency situation arose. The methodology is based on:

- Evaluating the boilers’ efficiency by dividing the swimming pool water energy demand (kWh_t) by the swimming pool water energy consumption (kWh_{pci}). The annual efficiency average of the boiler has been estimated to be 86,82%
- Knowing the main hybrid PV-T panels’ characteristics, a monthly thermal contribution from the CHESSE SETUP system has been estimated for the months where its optimal performance could not be achieved.

Total Sports Centre Consumption													
CHESS SETUP SYSTEM											BASELINE		
Month	Elect. Prod.	Electricity consumption				Total energy consumption					Total		
	PV-T (kWh _e)	f_PV-T (kWh _e)	f_Grid (kWh _e)	Total (kWh _e)	Surplus (kWh _e)	Electric (kWh _e)	Natural Gas (kWh _{PCI})	Electric Cost (€)	Natural Gas Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)	Natural Gas (kWh _{PCI})	Cost (€)	CO ₂ (kg)
Apr.	3.871	893	2.852	3.745	2.978	-126	227.350	-29,45 €	13.405,60 €	60.111	249.666	14,721.48 €	65.690
May	4.238	978	2.280	3.258	3.260	-980	173.207	-109,08 €	8.561,06 €	45.775	199.401	9,855.76 €	52.465
Jun.	5.222	1.205	310	1.515	4.017	-3.706	83.561	-362,42 €	4.176,47 €	21.886	108.863	5,441.06 €	28.643
Jul.	5.691	1.313	16	1.330	4.377	-4.361	38.027	-424,36 €	2.303,22 €	9.851	64.065	3,880.27 €	16.856
Aug.	5.792	1.337	32	1.368	4.456	-4.424	47.134	-430,55 €	2.832,92 €	12.247	74.181	4,458.54 €	19.518
Sep.	4.737	1.093	97	1.190	3.644	-3.546	111.636	-345,58 €	6.636,49 €	29.256	138.787	8.250,55 €	36.517
Oct.	1.578	640	1.811	2.451	938	873	204.031	61,03 €	12.006,38 €	53.932	218.545	12,860.44 €	57.502
Nov.	2.148	395	2.073	2.468	1.753	320	167.894	21,72 €	9.899,53 €	44.392	180.374	10,635.37 €	47.459
Dec.	1.626	413	1.737	2.150	1.213	524	304.582	57,93 €	17.845,31 €	80.343	315.027	18,457.28 €	82.888
Jan.	1.315	378	1.479	1.857	937	542	369.418	81,49 €	21.480,19 €	97.380	377.567	21,954.05 €	99.343
Feb.	2.416	509	2.009	2.518	1.907	102	207.812	-47,52 €	12.264,92 €	54.886	221.116	13,050.09 €	58.178
Mar.	2.972	474	1.619	2.093	2.498	-879	239.696	-95,29 €	14.123,96 €	63.182	250.801	14,778.34 €	65.989
TOTAL	41.604	9.629	16.316	25.944	31.976	-15.660	2.174.348	-1.622,07 €	125.536,06 €	573.239	2.398.393	138.343,24 €	631.049
SAVINGS [%]											9,34 %	10,43 %	9,16%
SAVINGS [kWh _{PCI} , € _t and kgCO ₂]											224.045	14.429,25	57.810

Table 16: Comparative table between CHESS SETUP energy generation and consumption and baseline consumption of Sant Cugat's Sport Centre

In the monitored period (September 2019 to March 2020), the energy supplied by the system to satisfy the swimming-pool water heating demand is distributed as shown in the Figure 25. During this period, the CHESS SETUP system provided about 21% of the energy needed to cover the swimming-pool water thermal demand. The remaining heating was supplied by the boiler.

Figure 25: CHESS SETUP system energy demand

If the analysis consumption is extended to a period of one year as indicated in Table 16, the CHESS SETUP system should be capable of supplying 31% of the 'swimming-pool water' heating thermal demand, a total amount of 224.045 kWh_{pci} as primary thermal energy savings. This represents 9,3% of primary thermal energy savings of the Sports Centre.

Regarding the electrical energy consumption of the CHESS SETUP system, for the same period, the values observed in Figure 26 were registered. The blue line represents the energy consumed by the CHESS SETUP system, including the heat pump and auxiliaries' equipment. The yellow line indicates the electrical energy generated by the PV-T modules. Green columns for PV-T, and grey columns for Grid, show the source of the energy consumed by the system. Yellow columns show the monthly electrical surplus.

Figure 26: CHESSE SETUP electrical consumption and production

As shown in Table 16, for the period of one year the estimated total electrical consumption of the system is 25,9 MWh/year. This consumption is divided in two different sources: 9,6 MWh/year comes from the PV-T panels production and 16,3 MWh/year comes from the grid. The total electrical production from the PV-T panels is 41,6 MWh/year. Therefore, it has been estimated that the CHESSE SETUP system is providing 15,6 MWh/year as energy savings, which is totally consumed by the Sport Centre.

Although the electrical production in the monitored months was lower than expected, this was mainly due to two specific causes. In the first months of the CHESSE SETUP system operation, failures in three PV-T panels were detected and that had to be replaced (warranty). On the other hand, the disconnection of an inverter was caused by a string failure. These failures have already been fixed.

Figure 27 shows the daily average CHESSE SETUP system electrical production and consumption for different months. Although, in October and January the energy consumption of the CHESSE SETUP system (orange tone) has a greater coincidence with the energy produced by the PV-T panels (yellow), in the four months the system helps to reduce the electricity peak consumption from the grid (grey) at peak hours. It should be remembered that the entire electrical surplus produced by the PV-T panels (green) is self-consumed by the sports centre.

Figure 27: CHESSETUP average daily electrical consumption and production for different months

Summarizing, the CHESSETUP system provides an annual estimated gas consumption savings of 224.045 kWh_{pci}, 9,3 % of the Sports Centre thermal demand compared to the baseline case. In addition, it is estimated to provide an annual electrical savings of 15,6 MWh_e. This also represents an estimated energy cost savings of approximately 14.000 Euros per year for the Sports Centre, comparing the pilot with the baseline case. Finally, it is also important to mention the considerable saving in greenhouse gas emissions, close to 58 tCO₂/year, 9,2 % of the total Sport Centre gas emissions, as shown in Figure 28

Figure 28: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions to supply the Sports Centre thermal demand

Figure 29 shows the difference in energy use and carbon emissions to supply the 'swimming-pool water' heating demand, if we consider the savings of the CHESSE SETUP system in relation to the baseline case (boiler) for supplying the water' thermal demand, the saving in gas consumptions are 30,4 % and in emissions are 30 %.

Figure 29: Difference in energy use and carbon emissions to supply the 'swimming-pool water' heating demand.

In deliverables D3.7 and D5.1, after carried out the simulations and data analysis of the CHESSE SETUP system performance, a total thermal energy saving of 187 MWh/year and a photovoltaic production of 60 MWh/year were expected to obtain for this pilot. In addition, for the Sports Centre a total of 65 tCO₂/year of emission savings were estimated.

To calculate the avoided CO₂ emissions, the methodology developed in the deliverable 'D4.3 Integration with the electrical system' has been used, where the emission factors of the electrical network were considered for the case of Sant Cugat pilot (Red Eléctrica de España SA, 2020), as well as the natural gas emission factors for the respective countries¹⁷. For a conservative estimation of the emissions avoided, the carbon footprint of PV panels is considered equal to 80 gCO₂/kWh (panels manufactured in economies dominated by coal)¹⁸.

Although the monitoring of the system has not been possible for one year period, the data obtained from the period of September to March made it possible to know in detail the system operation and their expected performance in cold periods (autumn and winter). Energy and emissions savings are in line with estimates in previous

¹⁷ https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/factores_emision_tcm30-479095.pdf

¹⁸ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/grantham-institute/public/publications/briefing-papers/Solar-power-for-CO2-mitigation---Grantham-BP-11.pdf>

deliverables for the same period. The results obtained in Sant Cugat's Sports Centre are in line with those expected in the deliverables D3.7 and D5.1

The deliverable D6.1 presents an analysis of the economic savings generated by the CHESSETUP system for each pilot. This analysis is performed based on the energy savings, thermal and electrical, presented in this document.

3.3.3.3. Seasonal thermal energy storage

Analysing the STES behaviour for the monitored period, Figure 30 shows the daily STES average temperature variation. Lines in orange tones represent the daily average temperatures in the upper, middle and lower part of the tank. The blue line represents the average daily outdoor temperature. It can be seen that, with the exception of two specific cases in October and another two cases in December, the STES always offers an average daily temperature higher than the outside average temperature.

Figure 30: STES daily average temperatures vs. outdoor average temperature

Analysing the STES temperature peak at the beginning of February (T_{STES} middle, bottom and top), as shown in Figure 31, it was due to the fact that between January 28th and February 6th, there was practically no thermal demand from the swimming-pool for this period. The temperatures of the swimming-pool (T_{Spool_Water}) remained within limits, so the heat pump ($C_{STES_t_HP}$) and natural gas boiler ($C_{Boiler_t_pool}$) did not operate. Likewise, the period was of high radiation and temperature to be January ($T_{Outside}$), this caused the average temperature of the STES to rise from 14,7 °C to 31,7 °C. It was not until February 6 that the HP was automatically turned on for a period of approximately 8 hours.

Figure 31: Swimming pool and STES thermal variations, and temperatures between January 28th and February 10th.

From the values in Figure 30, the average STES temperatures (orange tone), and the maximum and minimum STES temperatures can be obtained for each month as shown in Figure 32. The wide range of temperatures in October, February or March is due to these are months of greater radiation and a moderated thermal demand. That is not the case for November, December and January where the thermal demand is higher and solar radiation is lower.

Figure 32: STES monthly average temperatures

Summarizing, in Figure 33 it can be seen that the average STES temperature is higher than the average outside temperature. As this pilot uses a water source heat pump (WSHP), the higher STES temperature comparing to the outside temperature helps to improve the performance of the heat pump, and consequently, the efficiency of the CHESSETUP system.

Figure 33: STES monthly average temperatures vs. outdoor monthly average temperatures

Figure 34 shows temperatures values (dashed lines) recorded every 5 minutes from the STES (lower, middle, top), the swimming-pool and the outside. It also shows the thermal transfer from the PV-T to the STES (C_PVT_t_STES), the heat transfer from the STES to the heat pump (C_STES_t_HP) and heat transfer directly from the STES to the swimming pool (C_STES_t_Pool), and the heat produced by the natural gas boiler (C_Boiler_t_Pool) and transferred directly to the swimming pool.

Figure 34: Swimming pool and STES thermal variations, and temperatures between January 26th and 27th.

Figure 34 corresponds to data collected from January 26th to 27th. As explained before, dashed lines correspond to temperatures values. It can be seen that when the temperature of the swimming-pool falls below its marked value, 0,2 °C below the set-

point temperature (30,0 °C), the heat pump is turned on (continuous blue line). When the STES temperature drops below the set minimum, the heat pump is turned off and the boiler is turned on (red lines) to satisfy the swimming-pool thermal demand. Once the pool temperature reaches 0,2 °C above the set-point temperature (30,2°C), the heat pump or boiler automatically turns off. On the other hand, Figure 34 also shows the heat contributed by the hybrid panels to the STES (light blue line). This transferred heat causes the temperature in the middle of the STES to increase from 13°C at 7:00 a.m. at 14.8 ° C at 12:15 h. which allows the heat pump to turn on again, but this time only to recharge the buffer. It is also observed how on January 27, the temperature of the pool falls below the established limit and the heat pump automatically starts operating from 9:30 a.m. until the desired temperature is reached. 4:15 p.m. approximately.

Finally, it is important to say that the system became operational in September 2019. Probably, if the STES had accumulated thermal energy during the months of highest radiation (spring and summer 2019), the average STES temperatures registered for the period from September to March would have been higher. However, the effect of the seasonal accumulation would occur from the next cold season (autumn 2020 onward).

3.3.3.4. Heat Pump performance

As already indicated in '3.3.3.2 Energy savings', the CHESSE SETUP system supplied 21 % of the 'swimming-pool water' thermal demand in the period from September 2019 to March 2020.

Table 17 shows the electrical energy consumption and thermal production values of the CHESSE SETUP system for the same period. It should be taken into consideration that the considered electrical energy consumption also includes the electrical consumption of auxiliaries' equipment such as hydraulic pumps, control and monitoring system. Therefore, the energy efficiency ratio (EER) obtained is the coefficient corresponding to the CHESSE SETUP system, including the heat pump.

Month	CHESSE SETUP energy consumption (kWh _e)	CHESSE SETUP thermal production (kWh _t)	EER
Oct.	2.451	12.686	5,2
Nov.	2.468	10.942	4,4
Dec.	2.149	9.048	4,2
Jan.	1.857	7.147	3,8
Feb.	2.518	11.619	4,6
Mar.	2.018	9.632	4,8
Total	13.462	61.078	4,5

Table 17: CHESSE SETUP heat pump energy performance

As can be seen in Table 14 and Figure 25, January was the month with the highest thermal demand. Similarly, Figure 30 and Figure 33 show that January has been the month with the lowest temperatures (absolute and average). Although January average ambient temperature was 8,6 °C (with minimum temperatures registered below 0 °C), the monthly average temperature of the STES has remained at 14,9 °C. In this month the system contributed 7,1 MWh_t, with a sEER of 3,8. Figure 35 shows CHESSE SETUP system averages monthly EERs for the monitored period.

Figure 35: CHESSE SETUP system average monthly COP

The STES provides a stable temperature medium as a heat source for the heat pump. This allowed the CHESSE SETUP system to have an average COP of 3,8 in the coldest month with the highest thermal demand. On the other hand, in Table 17 it is observed that October was the month in which the CHESSE SETUP supplied the highest thermal demand to the pools (12,7 MWh_t), with the higher STES average temperature, this combination resulted in an average monthly COP of 5,2. During warm months the COP of the system will tend to be higher than the values registered so far. Therefore, it could be considered that seasonal COP resulting from the CHESSE SETUP system would be close 5,5 value estimated in D3.7 and D5.1.

3.3.4. Sant Cugat's CHESSE SETUP system implementation impact

The CHESSE SETUP system implemented in Sant Cugat's is a prototype for a Sports Centre building.

In order to accomplish the goals of the CHESSE-SETUP system implementation in the Sports Centre, has been studying the challenges and constraints, and different possibilities for the location of the thermal storage tank and its operability with the solar-hybrid panels and water source heat pump. The final solution uses hybrid solar panels as the energy production side of the system that stores the thermal energy in a tank (100 m³) and feeds an efficient water source heat pump.

Table 18 summarizes the results of the implementation of the CHESS SETUP system in the aforementioned pilot. The column 'Simulated' presents the values obtained as results of comparing the baseline case (2016) with the system simulated in the 'D3.7 Pilot experience report'. The column 'Monitored' presents the values obtained as a result of comparing the system operation (2019-2020) of the implemented system with the base line (natural gas boiler).

		Simulated	Monitored
Demands			
Heating and DHW Cons. (kWh _t /year)		1.731.058	2.398.393
Other electric cons. (kWh _e /year)		1.045.906	1.062.222
Configuration			
Total sqm (m ²)		826	826
Solar Panels surface (m ²)		264	264
Solar Panels Peak power (kWp)		41,60	41,60
STES Vol (m ³)		100	100
HP Cons. (kWh _e /year)		31.954	25.944
COP		5,50	4,86
Operation			
PV-T / PV production	Electrical (kWh _e /year)	60.376	41.604
	Thermal (kWh _e /year)	178.955	-
STES temp.	Min (°C)	20	11,9
	Max (°C)	45	42,5
	Average (°C)	26	19,7
Buffer temp.(°C)		45	43,9
Backup cons. (kWh _{pci} /year)		1.532.526	2.174.348
Savings			
Natural Gas	(kWh _{pci} /year)	198.532	224.045
	(%)	12,1%	9,34%
Electricity	(kWh _e /year)	28.123	15.660
	(%)	2,7%	1,8%
Total energy	(kWh/year)	226.655	239.705
	(%)	8,2%	8,3%
CO ₂	(kgCO ₂ /yr)	65.651	57.810
	(%)	12,1%	9,2%

Table 18: Simulated vs monitored CHESS SETUP system implementation impacts for Sant Cugat's Sports Centre

The CHESS SETUP system provides an annual estimated gas consumption savings of 224.045 kWh_{pci}, 9,34 % of the Sports Centre thermal demand compared to the baseline case. On the other hand, the Sports Centre as a whole presents a reduction in electricity consumption compared to the baseline case of 15.660 kWh_e (due to the electricity consumption of 22.954 kWh_e of the heat pump, less the savings from the production of photovoltaic energy, 41.604 kWh_e). The system represents a reduction of 8,3 % of the total energy consumption, and a reduction of 9,2 % of the greenhouse gases emissions (57,8 tCO₂/yr).

4. Conclusions

This report analyses the impact of the CHESSE SETUP system implementation in three different typologies (i.e. dwellings, sports centre and office building) in order to satisfy the heating, cooling and DHW demands.

The analysis has been performed according to the different case studies and different scenarios (i.e. baseline and Chess Setup system implemented). The behaviour of the three typologies of buildings has been simulated and afterwards compared with the data collected during the monitoring period.

Results show that the combination of a solar energy collection system (hybrid and/or photovoltaic panels) coupled with the use of a high-efficient heat pump increase the efficiency of the heating system, reducing the demand of primary energy (mainly natural gas) and also reducing the greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, if seasonal thermal energy storage (water tank or geothermal boreholes) is added, an improvement in the self-sufficiency and efficiency of the system is obtained.

An additional benefit that CHESSE SETUP system has is the possibility to decrease or shift the peak power consumption of the system. This could provide economics and GHG emissions savings, since generally the peak periods of the network coincide with the moments of greatest cost and carbon intensity of the energy mix.

Finally, the results obtained allow us to define relevant future work in order to improve the Chess Setup system implementation. Initially, the fraction of electrical self-consumption could increase by better matching the operation of the heat pump with the hours of greatest solar radiation. This could lead to future modifications in the volumes of the direct used tanks (buffers). Secondly, the efficiency of CHESSE SETUP system could be increased by integrating other energy systems (such as dehumidifiers).

5. Annex

The following document presents the hypotheses that have been considered in order to perform the analysis of the Lavola pilot operation.

By analysing the data extracted from the system, at the beginning of March errors were detected in the measurements of the calorimeter installed at the outlet of the heat pump.

WAT has analysed the possible causes of the measurement error:

1. Checking the calorimeter readings

1.1 Calorimeter operation

STEP 1: Verify that the values recorded in the SCADA of the control system are those that appear on the calorimeter display. WAT has contacted personnel who are in the pilot (LVL) to verify that the values observed in the SCADA are the same as those of the equipment display.

STEP 2: Verify the installation of the calorimeter and temperature probes. The installed calorimeter model is not configured; it is programmed according to the tube section. So there can be no configuration errors (soft / firm) ware.

The calorimeter has two energy registers E_1 and E_3 :

- E_1 is the Heat counter.
- E_3 is the Cold counter.

The calorimeter has two temperature probes:

- The probe t_1 (Inlet) that would be the one that goes to the impulse towards the consumption.
- Probe t_2 (Outlet) which would be the return from consumption.

If $\Delta t = t_1 - t_2 > 0 \Rightarrow$ Positive power, Increase energy to E_1 (Heat).

If $\Delta t = t_1 - t_2 < 0 \Rightarrow$ Negative power, Increase energy to E_3 (Cold).

In the calorimeter model Multical 603 (Lavola) there is one more parameter, Θ_c which is at 25 °C by default. It can be programmed from the screen, but no one should have touched it:

- The calorimeter accumulates in E_1 when: $\Delta t > 0$ i $t_1 > \Theta_c$ (25 °C)
- The calorimeter accumulates in E_3 when: $\Delta t < 0$ i $t_1 < \Theta_c$ (25 °C)

1.2 Problematic:

The parameter Θ_c appears in the manual, it even indicates how to modify it, but the manual does not explain what it is, so the manufacturer is consulted. This parameter precisely acts as a filter to eliminate incorrect power when integrating.

For example, if heat is being generated at 50 °C and $t_1 > t_2$, if $\Theta_c = 25$ °C, all power at a temperature lower than $t_1 < 25$ °C will not accumulate heat energy. This can happen depending on what processes the machine does in its cycles. Filtering also applies to heat.

Lavola's main issue:

- It has been detected that in the calorimeter installed in Lavola, the temperature probes t_1 and t_2 are turned. In a calorimeter without filters this would only imply that the energy is accumulated to the opposite counter (Heat in E_3 and Cold in E_1).

- Since there is the filter $\Theta_c = 25$ °C:

1. When the heat pump supplies Heat, it works around 50 °C with a Δt of about 4 °C, therefore, more or less at 48 °C and 52 °C. If the probes are rotated, it remains that:

$$t_1=48 \text{ °C}; t_2=52 \text{ °C}; \Delta t=-4 \text{ °C} \rightarrow \text{It is time to accumulate in } E_3 \text{ (Cold)}$$

$$t_1 > \Theta_c \rightarrow \text{Does not accumulate!}$$

2. When the heat pump produces Cold, it works around 15 °C with a Δt of about 4 °C, therefore, more or less at 12 °C and 16 °C. If the probes are rotated, it remains that:

$$t_1=16 \text{ °C}; t_2=12 \text{ °C}; \Delta t=4 \text{ °C} \rightarrow \text{accumulates in } E_1 \text{ (Heat)}$$

$$t_1 < \Theta_c \rightarrow \text{Does not accumulate!}$$

3. Therefore, what has accumulated up to this moment (2020-05-07) in the E_1 and E_3 counters is precisely what we want to filter with $\Theta_c = 25$ °C, in the Heat E_1 counter, the energy of Cold residual by the cycles of the machine when doing Heat and in the one of Cold E_3 the energy of residual Heat due to the cycles of the machine when doing Cold.

SOLUTION: Turn the temperature probes t_1 (Inlet) and t_2 (Outlet)

2. Obtaining data for the period

2.1. Records in the Database.

In the database there are registered:

- 10/5/221. Temperature value t_1 (Inlet) [°C].
- 10/5/222. Temperature value t_2 (Outlet) [°C].
- 10/5/216. Energy E_1 (Residual cold from when Heat is made) [kWh]. Not useful.
- 10/5/217. Energy E_3 (Residual heat from when it becomes Cold) [kWh]. Not useful.
- 10/5/213. Positive and negative instantaneous power. Due to a firmware error in the M-BUS-KNX gateway, negative values are sent with an incorrect value that has been filtered in the DB.

2.2. Records in the calorimeter.

With an optical reader, the following values can be read directly from the calorimeter:

- Quarter-Hour Records: 1344 records (14 days)
- Time Records: 1440 hours (60 days)
- Daily Records: 460 days
- Monthly records: 36 months
- Annual registrations: 20 years

2.3. Conclusion on Data

Based on the data set out above:

- Boiler: The control system records indicate that the boiler has not been turned on since 2019-09-16, where some test had to be carried out since it would not make sense for it to work that day (summer).
- Chiller: It has only been turned on in a punctual way during the start-up of the heat pump, and in the register of specific faults. Since 2019-09-16 no fault has been recorded in the system, nor signals to turn on the chiller plant.
- Cold / Heat Configuration: The system automatically through the control has been producing Cold from 2019-07-26 to 2019-10-14, and Heat from 2019-10-15 to 2020-06-01.

- Cold records are available at the power level to be able to integrate them from 2019/09/20 to 2019/10/14. A daily aggregated integration of the positive power registered in the database with a 60-second filter is carried out, directly without interpolation, only with the power and consecutive registered times and applying the filter (consecutive measurements $\leq 60s$).

Based on the above, the data used for the system performance analysis are:

- 2020-09-20 to 2020-10-14 Cold production (kWh): data obtained from the positive integration every 60 seconds of the power.
- 2019-10-15 to 2020-05-31 Heat production (kWh): For which a linear approximation has been made considering:
 - Historical natural gas consumption of the existing boiler (2017-01 to 2019-05)
 - Seasonal efficiency of the boiler
 - Heating degree days (2017-01 to 2020-05) with base temperature 18 °C
- 2020-06-01 to 2020-09-19 Cold production (kWh): For which an approximation has been made considering:
 - Historical electricity consumption of the chiller plant (2012-05 to 2019-07)
 - Seasonal efficiency of the chiller plant
 - COP from heat pump
- 2020-05-01 to 2020-07-31 Photovoltaic production (kWh): based on the historic registered data.

